

LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF AN INTEGRATED PVT-BTES-HEAT PUMP SYSTEM FOR A COMMERCIAL SWINE FARM IN ITALY

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ABSTRACT

This study performed a Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) of an innovative energy system deployed at a commercial swine farm in Italy. The integrated Renewable Energy Sources (RES) system combines Photovoltaic-Thermal (PVT) panels, Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES), and a Heat Pump (HP) to provide heating to the farm's nursery barn, where 13,500 weaners are produced annually. The system is designed to harness solar energy through PVT panels, simultaneously generating electricity and heat. Excess thermal energy during summer is stored in the BTES for use during the winter period when the HP efficiently exploits the thermal energy of the outdoor air and/or the BTES.

The LCIA considered the raw material extraction, manufacturing, transportation, and installation phases for each system's components separately. The environmental load for all PVT, HP and BTES components was expressed per 1 kg of weaned piglets at the gate of the nursery barn. Primary data, such as bills of materials, were collected from the farm and technology providers. International secondary datasets and literature were used to model the upstream processes. The Environmental Footprint (v3.1) methodology as available in the SimaPro 9.5 software was implemented for estimating the environmental impact category indicators. The use of fossil fuels (RUF) and climate change (CC) were identified within the impact categories connected with higher indicator estimates per kg of weaned piglets at the farm gate for all PVT (RUF: 0.03MJ; CC: 2.14g CO₂eq), BTES (RUF: 0.004MJ; CC: 0.26g CO₂eq) and HP (RUF: 0.004MJ; CC: 0.28g CO₂eq) technologies.

These results will be used to investigate the potential environmental performance improvement of weaned piglets production which is associated with the installation of this integrated RES system.

Keywords: Life Cycle Assessment, Commercial Swine Farming, LCA datasets, Renewable Energy Sources systems